

A Study to Evaluate Ease of Laryngoscopy and Intubation by Use of Upper Lip Bite Test, Modified Mallampati Classification and Thyromental Distance

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Abstract:

Background: The occurrence of difficult intubation during general anesthesia ranges between 1% and 18%, while the rate of intubation failure is estimated to be around 0.05% to 0.35%. Various methods have been employed to predict difficult laryngoscopy, but consistent validation across different populations is essential for any test to become a standard practice. The Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT) has shown potential in its initial studies, but requires further validation. In this study, we compared the ULBT, Modified Mallampati Classification (MMC), and Thyromental Distance (TMD), both individually and in combination, to determine which tests are most significantly associated with difficult glottic exposure.

Methods: Following approval from the institutional ethics committee, we included 402 adult patients (ASA I and II) scheduled for elective surgeries requiring endotracheal intubation. Preoperatively, all patients underwent ULBT, MMC, and TMD assessments, and their glottic exposure was classified using the Cormack-Lehane scale during intubation. We analyzed the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of each test to compare their effectiveness.

Results: The study found that 11.4% of patients experienced difficult laryngoscopy, with a 0.49% rate of intubation failure. When used individually, none of the three tests demonstrated strong predictive ability. However, combining the tests provided an incremental increase in diagnostic accuracy.

Conclusion: Our findings suggest that ULBT, MMC, and TMD, when used alone, have only limited ability to predict difficult intubation. However, combining these tests offers improved diagnostic value, though still not definitive. Further research is needed to develop more reliable screening methods for predicting difficult intubation.

Keywords: Difficult Airway, Mallampati Classification, Thyromental Distance, Upper Lip Bite.

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Introduction

In the critical field of anesthesiology and emergency medicine, airway management stands as a cornerstone of patient safety. The ability to predict and manage difficult intubations can mean the difference between life and death. Yet, despite advances in medical technology and techniques, accurately forecasting the ease of laryngoscopy and intubation remains a complex challenge fraught with uncertainty and risk. [1]

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of three predictive tests - the Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT), Modified Mallampati Classification (MMC), and Thyromental Distance (TMD) - both

individually and in combination, to determine their efficacy in predicting the ease of intubation. By doing so, we seek to enhance patient safety and improve procedural outcomes in anesthesiology.

Difficult Intubation: A Global Concern Difficult intubation occurs in approximately 1-18% of patients undergoing general anesthesia, with complete failure to intubate ranging from 0.05-0.35%. [2,3] While global statistics paint a concerning picture, the prevalence in India and specifically in Punjab may vary due to genetic and environmental factors. The combination of difficult intubation with general anesthesia further complicates the scenario,

potentially leading to severe consequences if not managed promptly and effectively. [5,6]

Complications and Consequences: The repercussions of difficult intubation are far-reaching and potentially devastating. Patients face increased risks of hypoxia, which can result in brain damage or death if prolonged. Airway trauma, aspiration, and extended anesthetic exposure are additional hazards. For healthcare providers, difficult intubations lead to heightened stress, prolonged procedure times, and increased resource utilization. In the most severe cases, emergency interventions such as cricothyrotomy may become necessary, carrying their own set of risks. [7,8,9]

A Solution on the Horizon: To address these challenges, the medical community has turned to predictive tests that can help identify patients at risk for difficult intubation before the procedure begins. By employing these tests, anesthesiologists can prepare alternative techniques and equipment, significantly improving patient outcomes. The ULBT, MMC, and TMD tests offer promise in this regard, each assessing different aspects of airway anatomy and function.

These tests work by evaluating specific anatomical features and physiological capabilities: [10,11,12]

- The Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT) assesses mandibular mobility and the ability to protrude the lower jaw.
- The Modified Mallampati Classification (MMC) categorizes the visibility of oropharyngeal structures.
- The Thyromental Distance (TMD) measures the space available for laryngoscope manipulation.

By combining these tests, we aim to create a more comprehensive and accurate prediction model for difficult intubations.

As we delve into the efficacy of these predictive tools, a crucial question emerges: Can a combination of the ULBT, MMC, and TMD tests significantly improve our ability to foresee and manage difficult intubations, thereby enhancing patient safety and procedural success in Anaesthesiology?

Materials and Methods

After obtaining approval from the institutional ethics committee and written informed consent from 402 patients over a period of 2 months we conducted a prospective, double-blind study to evaluate three predictive tests—Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT), Modified Mallampati Classification (MMC), and Thyromental Distance (TMD)—for their effectiveness in predicting the ease of laryngoscopy and intubation.

Participants included ASA I and II patients over 18 years old undergoing elective surgery with endotracheal intubation. We excluded patients with conditions like previous airway surgeries, burns, tumors, restricted neck or jaw mobility, edentulism, pregnancy, or a BMI over 26 kg/m². Preoperative airway assessments were done. ULBT, MMC and TMD tests were performed on the day of the surgery, bedside.

Test Details:

Airway Assessment Tools

1. Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT)

Procedure: Patients were seated with their head in a neutral position. They were asked to bite their upper lip with their lower incisors as high as possible. The anesthetist demonstrated the test to ensure correct patient compliance, following the method described by the original authors [5].

Classification:

Class	Description
Class I	Lower incisors can bite the upper lip above the vermillion border
Class II	Lower incisors can bite the upper lip below the vermillion border
Class III	Lower incisors cannot bite the upper lip

Figure 1: Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT) [4]

2. Modified Mallampati Classification (MMC)

Procedure: Patients were seated with their head in a neutral position, mouth wide open, tongue fully protruded, and without phonation ("ah"). A torch was used to visualize the oral structures [8,9,10].

Classification:

Class	Description
Class I	Full visibility of the soft palate, uvula, and tonsillar pillars.
Class II	Visibility of the soft palate and the upper portion of the uvula.
Class III	Visibility of the soft palate and the base of the uvula.
Class IV	Only the hard palate is visible.

Figure 2: The Modified Mallampati classification [4]

3. Thyromental Distance (TMD)

Procedure: With the patient seated upright and neck fully extended, the distance from the mentum to the superior notch of the thyroid cartilage was measured using a ruler. A TMD of less than 6 cm was considered significant.

Category	Description
Class 1	TMD > 6.5 cm (Indicates sufficient mandibular space for intubation)
Class 2	TMD between 6.0 - 6.5 cm (Indicates moderate difficulty in intubation)
Class 3	TMD < 6.0 cm (Indicates potential difficulty in intubation)

Figure 3: Thyromental Distance [4]

Anaesthesia and Induction

Monitoring: Standard monitors (electrocardiogram, automated blood pressure, pulse oximetry, end-tidal carbon dioxide) were attached.

Intravenous access was established with a 20G cannula, and Lactated Ringer's solution was administered at 2 ml/kg/hr.

Pre-Sedation: Five minutes prior to induction, patients received midazolam (0.05 mg/kg) and butorphanol (2 mcg/kg). Pre-oxygenation was performed for 3–4 minutes with 100% oxygen.

Induction: General anaesthesia was induced with propofol (2 mg/kg) and the neuromuscular relaxant atracurium (0.5 mg/kg). Ventilation was with oxygen and nitrous oxide (50%).

Laryngoscopy

Positioning: After 4 minutes, the patient's head was placed in the optimal sniffing position (neck flexed on the chest, head elevated with a head ring, and head extended at the atlanto-occipital joint).

Procedure: Laryngoscopy was performed with a Macintosh 3 blade by an anaesthesiologist with at least one year of experience. The laryngoscope view was graded using the Cormack-Lehane (CL) grading system without external laryngeal manoeuvres [15].

- Grade 1: Most of the glottis visible.
- Grade 2: Only the posterior part of the glottis and epiglottis visible.
- Grade 3: Only the epiglottis visible.
- Grade 4: Not even the epiglottis seen.

Classification of Laryngoscopy Ease

1. Easy Laryngoscopy: CL Grade 1 and 2.
2. Difficult Laryngoscopy: CL Grade 3 and 4.

Procedure: On the day of surgery, standard monitoring was applied, and anesthesia was induced using propofol and vecuronium, followed by ventilation with oxygen, nitrous oxide, and isoflurane. The patient was positioned in the optimal sniffing position for laryngoscopy, performed by an anaesthesiologist with at least one year of experience. The laryngoscopic view was graded using the Cormack-Lehane system, with grades 1 and 2 indicating easy laryngoscopy and grades 3 and 4 indicating difficulty.

In cases where intubation was difficult, external laryngeal maneuvers were attempted, and if

necessary, the procedure was taken over by the most experienced anesthetist present. A Proseal laryngeal mask airway was on standby for cases of intubation failure.

Data Analysis: Data were entered into an Excel worksheet and analyzed using SPSS 16.0 software. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) were calculated to compare the predictive accuracy of the tests.

Methodology

Study Design and Participants: All patients underwent a comprehensive preoperative airway assessment. This assessment was conducted by a single anesthetist to ensure consistency and minimize inter-observer bias.

Results

In this study, the age of the patients ranged from 18 to 80 years, with an average age of 41.89 years and a standard deviation of 14.356 years. Out of the 402 patients, 108 were male, and 294 were female. The higher number of female participants can be attributed to the inclusion of patients scheduled for gynecological procedures and general surgeries like hysterectomy. The mean BMI of the participants was 22.1689, with a standard deviation of 1.63.

We assessed the predictive accuracy of the Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT), Modified Mallampati Classification (MMC), and Thyromental Distance (TMD) independently, in pairs, and in combination. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) for each test and their combinations are detailed in Table 1.

To present the predictive values for the Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT), Modified Mallampati Classification (MMC), and Thyromental Distance (TMD), along with their combinations, for predicting the occurrence of Cormack-Lehane (CL) Grade 3 or 4 laryngoscopic views, you can create the table as follows:

Table 1: Predictive Values of ULBT, MMC, TMD, and Their Combinations for Predicting CL Grade 3 or 4 Laryngoscopic View

Tests	Predicted easy intubations (%)	Predicted difficult intubations (%)	Sensitivity	Specificity	Positive predictive value	Negative predictive value
ULBT	97.8	2.2	98.6	8.7	89.3	44.4
MMC	81.1	11.9	90.4	30.4	91	29.2
TMD	87.3	12.7	90.2	34.8	91.5	31.4
ULBT+MMC	85.8	14.2	88.8	37	91.6	29.8
ULBT+TMD	85.8	14.2	89	39.1	91.9	31.6
MMC+TMD	77.1	22.9	80.9	52.2	92.9	26.1
ULBT+MMC+TMD	76.1	23.9	80.3	56.5	93.5	27.1

Our findings showed that 46 out of 402 patients experienced difficult laryngoscopy, but nearly all of these cases were successfully intubated using external laryngeal maneuvers. This highlights that a difficult laryngoscopy doesn't always equate to a difficult intubation. The Cormack-Lehane classification, which assesses glottic exposure, is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Cormack-Lehane classification of glottic exposure

	No. of patients	Percentage
Easy laryngoscopy	356	88.6
Difficult laryngoscopy	46	11.4
Total	402	100

Only two patients could not be intubated despite multiple attempts by the most experienced personnel, and both were successfully ventilated using a Proseal laryngeal mask airway. Of these two cases, one was anticipated as difficult, while the other was not. Notably, no incidents of desaturation occurred during the study.

While ULBT alone may not be a reliable predictor of difficult intubation, its combination with MMC or TMD significantly improves sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV. When all three tests are combined, they offer the highest specificity, an acceptable sensitivity, and a comparable PPV and NPV to the other tests. This suggests that using a combination of these tests provides incremental diagnostic value and is more effective for predicting difficult intubation.

Discussion

Difficult tracheal intubation accounts for around 17% of adverse respiratory events according to an analysis by the American Society of Anesthesiologists' Closed Claims Project. In 85% of these cases, the outcome was either death or hypoxic brain damage[^] [16]. Difficult intubation also increases the risk of critical, non-fatal events such as desaturation, hypertension, esophageal intubation, upper airway and dental trauma, delayed surgeries, prolonged hospital stays, and increased admissions to intensive care units. Accurately predicting difficult airways before surgery allows time to develop a proper management plan.

Various tests have been developed to predict difficult laryngoscopy and intubation. However, unanticipated difficult intubations often occur due to the lack of accurate predictive tests. Additionally, the intubation skills of the practitioner are challenging to standardize in assessments. In our study, 18 colleagues with clinical experience ranging from 1 to 35 years performed the intubations. This diversity is crucial for validating a clinical tool intended for routine screening use.

Though numerous studies have explored unanticipated difficult intubation, there is wide variability in the sensitivity of different predictive tests. The ideal preoperative airway assessment method

should have high sensitivity and specificity, minimizing both false positives and false negatives.

Our study revealed that when used alone, the Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT) demonstrated good sensitivity (98.6%) but very low specificity (8.7%). Typically, an increase in one of these metrics leads to a decrease in the other. Compared to ULBT alone, the Modified Mallampati Classification (MMC) or Thyromental Distance (TMD) proved to be better predictors. Combining these tests further enhanced their diagnostic value.

In 2005, Eberhart et al. assessed ULBT in a sample of 1,425 patients but could not replicate the high predictive properties originally reported for the test [17]. They found that MMC was a better predictor than ULBT but concluded that both tests were poor predictors of difficult laryngoscopy and intubation when used alone.

Studies by Cattano et al. in the Italian population concluded that the Mallampati score by itself is insufficient for predicting difficult endotracheal intubation [14]. Similarly, Huh et al., through univariate analysis, found MMC to be inferior to TMD as a predictive test. However, they noted that combining tests added incremental diagnostic value [18]. Krobbuaban et al. found that Mallampati class 3 or 4 was a significant predictor of difficult laryngoscopy, but interestingly, they observed no correlation between TMD <6.5 cm and difficult laryngoscopy [19].

Khan et al., both in the original study and a subsequent study in 2011, found ULBT to be a very good predictor compared to other indices when used as a single screening test [16]. They discovered that a higher ULBT score had a strong positive correlation with a higher Cormack-Lehane (CL) grade during laryngoscopy. However, unlike in our study, their preoperative airway assessments were done by two evaluators, introducing inter-observer bias. Hester et al. also found ULBT to be a superior predictor compared to MMC [20]. Safavi et al. reported that ULBT alone was a better predictor of difficult laryngoscopy than MMC, either alone or in combination with ULBT [21]. Chohedri et al. found ULBT to have higher specificity and accuracy than MMC and TMD but noted that TMD was the most sensitive test for predicting difficult lar-

ngoscopy [22]. Gupta et al., in a study of the Kashmiri population, ranked the predictor tests based on their association with difficult intubation, finding poor Mallampati class and TMD <6 cm significantly associated with difficult intubation [23].

Shiga et al., in a meta-analysis, found that MMC had greater discriminative power than TMD as a predictor of difficult intubation. They also observed that the positive likelihood ratio of TMD improved from 3.4 to 4.1 when a stricter cut-off criterion (<6.0 cm) was applied [3]. Although other studies have compared ULBT with TMD, none have examined their combined predictive value. The increasing specificity observed with the MMC + TMD combination in our study demonstrates the greater diagnostic value of combining these tests. Frek et al. also reported high sensitivity and specificity (81.2% and 97.8%, respectively) for this combination [15].

Some studies included the original Mallampati test, which had only three classes, while we used the Samssoon and Young's Modified Mallampati test, which has been shown to have better predictive value [24,27]. Our study found that combining all three tests provided the highest specificity for predicting difficult intubation. However, since no single test or combination of tests can uniformly predict all cases of difficult glottic exposure, it is important to recognize the dynamic relationship between sensitivity and specificity. Using multiple preoperative predictor tests can reduce the frequency of both unanticipated failures to visualize laryngeal structures and unnecessary interventions due to over-prediction of airway difficulty.

We faced several challenges during our study. Despite demonstrating ULBT to patients, some had difficulty following instructions, likely due to anxiety or repeated attempts to achieve the correct position. Additionally, this test is not appropriate for edentulous patients, who had to be excluded. Dental literature also shows significant racial variations in the morphology of human mandible and maxillary bones [21]. Tham et al. confirmed that preventing phonation during MMC grading is crucial for reliable scoring¹⁰. Spontaneous phonation occurs in about 25% of patients, leading to inter-observer variability [19,28]. Additionally, there are many sources of error in TMD measurement, including digital preference, rounding, different landmarks, and head positions, all contributing to inter-observer variability [24]. To avoid this, all observations in our study were performed by a single anesthetist [18,29]. Various studies have used different TMD cut-off values (ranging from 4 to 7 cm) for predicting difficult intubation [13,14,19,28,29]. In our study, a TMD less than 6 cm was considered predictive of difficult intubation, consistent with the original article by Patil et al. and the meta-

analysis by Shiga et al. [4,3]. It is crucial that clinicians understand the limitations of all predictive tests and remain prepared to follow appropriate algorithms to avoid morbidity and mortality due to difficult airway mismanagement³⁰.

Variations in the incidence of difficult laryngoscopy have been attributed to different factors, such as variations in anthropomorphic features among populations, lack of uniformity in describing laryngeal views, the use of external laryngeal maneuvers, head position, degree of muscle relaxation, and the type or size of laryngoscope blade [21]. Research has primarily focused on predicting difficult laryngoscopy, as it is the most common cause of difficult intubation. However, while difficult laryngoscopy is a major determinant of difficult intubation, it is not synonymous with it. In many clinical situations, applying external laryngeal pressure improves the laryngoscopic view, allowing intubation to be performed without difficulty. Furthermore, direct laryngoscopy is not the only method for securing and maintaining an airway, although it is the most common means of facilitating intubation¹⁸.

As Wilson stated, "No test is likely to be perfect, therefore, it remains essential that every anesthetist must be trained and equipped to deal with the now much less common, unexpected failure to intubate" [3]. We realized that while attempts at prediction are important, knowing what to do when faced with difficulty is crucial.

Conclusions

In conclusion, currently available screening tests for difficult intubation have only poor to moderate discriminative power when used alone. Combining individual tests adds some incremental diagnostic value. However, the clinical value of these bedside screening tests for predicting difficult intubation remains limited. The search for the "Holy Grail" of a predictive test for difficult intubation continues. Given this, our efforts should not only focus on finding an ideal predictor test but also on intensifying the training of physicians in appropriate algorithms, as per the Difficult Airway Society guidelines, to prevent morbidity and mortality from mismanaged difficult airways.

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